

Predicting Hospital Readmission after Cancer Surgery with Survival Analysis and Machine Learning

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Abstract. Random survival forests are very useful in the prediction the time to the first hospital readmission and to model the effects of predictors on survival data with no assumptions. Their use is consequently constantly increasing in medical research. However, the clinical interest may rely in the multiple readmissions patients undergo. As a result, we have adapted these forests to survival data with multiple event occurrences, referred as recurrent events, in the presence or absence of a fatal event. The aim of this work is to introduce the use of **RecForest** to help understanding the burden of disease after cancer surgery. Our approach is in five steps, to i) discern the relevance of multiple and fatal events, ii) develop trees and build the forest, iii) thoroughly evaluate performance, iv) provide the importance of variables, and v) enable predictions on new data. Data from hospital readmission in metastatic colorectal cancer patients were used to illustrate our purpose.

Keywords: Machine learning · Survival analysis · Recurrent events.

1 Introduction

Machine learning models, such as random forests, are used increasingly in time-to-event analysis. In particular, random survival forests (RSFs) are now widely used in survival analysis [1]. Yet when faced with multiple event occurrences, referred as recurrent events, such as hospital readmissions, conventional survival analysis, and hence RSFs, only considers the time to the first instance. In such cases, clinical studies have been carried out to overcome the issue of recurrent events either by considering the overall number of events using counting processes (without taking into account the time between two events), or by means of a binary classification problem involving the multiplicity of events (yes-no) [2].

To address this gap, we proposed an extended RSF called **RecForest** to recurrent events to predict the expected number of events for each patient over time. The aim of this work is to introduce the use of **RecForest** to help understanding the burden of disease through multiple hospital readmissions after cancer surgery.

2 Overview of the algorithm

Input data consists of several observations for each patient, with variables indicating the presence (or absence) of multiple events, the presence (or absence) of a terminal fatal event (TFE), the time associated with the occurrence of each event, and possible time-dependent or time-independent explanatory variables. **RecForest** works in a similar way to RSF algorithm [1]. For each bootstrap sample, survival trees adapted to multiple events are constructed. The forest aggregates the results obtained for each tree to obtain an overall estimate.

At each node, the aim is to discriminate as best as possible the data from *mtry* randomly selected variables. This discrimination is made according to the presence or absence of a TFE using the pseudo-score test statistic or the Wald test statistic of a Gosh-Lin marginal model [3,4]. The estimate is the expected number of events for each individual until time t , denoted $\hat{M}(t | x)$, which is the aggregation of estimates $\hat{\mu}(t | \mathbf{x})$ for each tree in the forest. Depending on the presence or absence of a TFE,

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{M}(t | x) &= \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \hat{\mu}_b(t | \mathbf{x}) \\ &= \begin{cases} = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \hat{R}_b(t | \mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \int_0^t \frac{N_b(du|\mathbf{x})}{Y_b(du|\mathbf{x})} & \text{with no TFE,} \\ = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{b=1}^B \int_0^t \hat{S}_b(u | \mathbf{x}) d\hat{R}_b(u | \mathbf{x}) & \text{with a TFE.} \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

with B the number of trees, \mathbf{x} a vector of time-dependent or time-independent predictors, N the number of node-specific events, Y the number of individuals at risk, \hat{S} the Kaplan-Meier estimator of the survival function.

Performance evaluation. Alongside this work, we also propose two metrics for assessing performance of models with recurrent events, both in terms of discrimination with a concordance index (C-index) and calibration with an integrated mean square error (IMSE) extension [5,6].

Interpretability of RecForest. Machine learning algorithms often fail to provide interpretable outputs. As a solution, we propose an importance-based approach to assist in clinical decision-making.

3 Results

The **readmission** data are frequently used for methodological principles and contains the hospital readmissions of 403 colorectal cancer patients as per Figure 1A [7].

Metrics showed strong model performance with average (standard error) values of C-index = 0.80 (0.04) (best when close to 1) and IMSE = 706.02 (508.96) (the lower the better). Variable importance for **RecForest** was based on both the C-index and the opposite of the integrated MSE (Figure 1B). Most important variable identified by **RecForest** was the Charlson comorbidity index. Prediction curves were generated for two patients, one with the highest Charlson comorbidity score (in orange), and the other with the lowest (in blue) in 1C.

Fig. 1. RecForest on readmission data. **A** is the recurrent event description plot, **B** depicts variable importance and **C** predictions with new data.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, we have introduced a new algorithm based on survival theory for recurrent events with or without a terminal fatal event, and an ensemble-based learning methodology. RecForest is readily available to adequately address other clinical needs (R package coming very soon).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare no conflict of interest. Author Murriss J reports a grant from the ANRT, with Pierre Fabre, Convention industrielle de formation par la recherche number 2020/1701.

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